

DATABASE PLANNING

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Abstract. In the article, the organization of the database life cycle, database planning, database design, database administration, the use of file structures of vase interaction in the organization of effective access to information, relationship in the database information is provided describing the limits and safety measures.

Key words: Administration, planning, integration, planning, conceptual model, physical model, logical model.

ПЛАНИРОВАНИЕ БАЗЫ ДАННЫХ

Аннотация. В статье приводятся организация жизненного цикла базы данных, планирование базы данных, проектирование базы данных, администрирование базы данных, использование файловых структур вазы, взаимодействие в организации эффективного доступа к информации, взаимосвязь в информации базы данных с описанием ограничений. и меры безопасности.

Ключевые слова: Администрирование, планирование, интеграция, планирование, концептуальная модель, физическая модель, логическая модель.

A MB administrator is a person or group of people who design, transmit and ensure the effective operation of MB. There is also a customer bank interface with a database icon. The concept of data bank (MB) has two different interpretations. Currently, in most cases, the database is organized in a decentralized manner. Therefore, data bank and database are also used as synonyms. !. In the basic interpretation, a data bank is understood as a database management system (MBBT). A program that works with a database is called an application. A single database can handle a lot.

Advantages of using MB »i: - Compactness; - Increasing the speed of information processing; - Low labor cost; SQL Server security tools can be used with SQL Server Enterprise Manager. Information about these protections is available from the SQL Server documentation. If you may need to change the encrypted image structure later, use the following advice. Save the SQL statement defining the image to a text file. Use your imagination. Change the structure of the encrypted image as necessary: Delete the previous encrypted image. Create a new image with the same name as the previous image. Copy the SQL statement from the saved text file to the clipboard. Change the structure of imagination. 0 Save the modified SQL statement to a text file. Place this file in a safe place. SQL Server account management can be done using the (Database Security) item in the (Tools) menu. You can use this command if SQL Server is installed on the computer where the project is stored. Using this tool, you can create accounts for registration in SQL Server, database users You can add, delete, and modify entries and link assignments. SQL Server has two security systems used for logging: SQL Server's own security system. To register on the server, you need to specify the server user name and password. The system integrated with Windows NT uses user accounts. In this case, user authentication is performed through registration

on a network based on Windows NT. Using procedures in SQL increases the efficiency of programming. A stored procedure is a set of SQL statements that SQL SERVER compiles once. Stored procedures will not be compiled on the next use of the procedure. These procedures can also have input parameters, just like in algorithmic languages. Stored procedures are created in SQL using the following statement:

```
CREATE PROCEDURE <procedure name>  
[(% first parameter information type)J ...] AS SQL- operators;
```

There are two types of stored procedures: user procedures! and systematic procedures. User procedures are stored in SQL SERVERS. used to manage the server, get information about MB and users. System procedures are created to execute application programs. Applications should always contain a single module. A module (MODULE) is an object created in an algorithmic language and stored for a long time.

A module consists of a module name, an algorithmic language clause, a module authorization clause, a declaration cursor, and one or more procedures. MBBT is used by two groups of people:

1. Limited or ordinary users;
2. MB administrator!. The service scope of the MB administrator includes the following tasks:
3. Analysis of the subject area and determining the location of users and information;
4. Development of data structure and their improvement;
5. Ensuring integrity of assigned tasks and information;
6. Loading and maintaining MB;
7. Data protection;
8. To ensure restoration of MB;
9. Collection and statistical processing of appeals to the MB;
10. Prevent data from being deleted when working in MB multi-user mode;
11. When technical equipment malfunctions

It changes dynamically due to the increase of information in the database. New data elements are added to it. New connections or dependencies are created between them, and new methods of processing are introduced. In this process, as much as possible, the developer tries to make as little changes to the software application that was created to work with the MB that the developer created. This problem can be solved by logically grouping data elements into groups and defining keys for them. Today, manufacturers of information systems offer to use data in third normal form. The concept of functional dependence. In relational MB, attention is paid not only to the data structure, but also to their schematic information. Information about the structure of the MB is provided using a relational scheme. Schematic information is represented by functional relationships between attributes. In MB relations, the composition of attributes should be grouped in such a way as to meet the following requirements: - Unnecessary repetitions between attributes should not occur. - When grouping attributes, the repetition of values should be kept to a minimum. This allows for quick processing of direct products. This is achieved using the normalization process. Normalization means dividing a given relationship into several simple and small relationships. In this process, all possible functional dependencies are identified.

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